

RADIOFREQUENCY ABLATION OF UTERINE FIBROIDS: ADVANCING MINIMALLY INVASIVE TREATMENT FOR WOMEN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15068106>

Introduction: Uterine fibroids, or leiomyomas, are benign smooth muscle tumors of the uterus that affect a significant proportion of women during their reproductive years. While many fibroids are asymptomatic, symptomatic cases can lead to significant morbidity, including abnormal uterine bleeding, pelvic pain, and infertility. Traditional treatment options include hysterectomy, myomectomy, and uterine artery embolization (UAE) but their morbidity rate was not satisfactory. Radiofrequency ablation has emerged as a promising technique, offering a minimally invasive approach that targets fibroids directly while preserving the surrounding healthy tissue and uterine integrity. This approach is increasingly recognized for its effectiveness and patient-centered benefits. Radiofrequency ablation of uterine fibroids is a minimally invasive treatment modality for uterine fibroids, offering an effective alternative to the traditional surgical interventions. This technique is particularly suitable for women seeking symptom relief with minimal recovery time, desire for future fertility and a low risk of complications.

The aim of this research is to study the pregnancy outcomes and the morbidity rates after laparoscopic and transcervical radiofrequency ablation of fibroids.

Materials and methods: Study design and Population: Patients were identified from case reports and case series of pregnancies following trials of radiofrequency ablation for symptomatic uterine fibroids. Study was conducted at Nazareth Hospital, India with Dr. Neha Gupta and colleague Dr. Kalashree where we collected case histories of 44 patients with symptomatic Uterine fibroids who has undergone RFA. The Sonata System technology was used for this procedure including intraoperative ultrasound guidance and monitoring of the fibroids. Certain inclusion and exclusion criteria were considered before selecting patients favourable for this procedure which included their Reproductive age or women of older age, symptomatic uterine fibroids confirmed by transvaginal USG and MRI, ≤ 12 week uterine size, $< 300\text{cm}^3$

fibroid volume and atleast three months of heavy menstrual bleeding within 6 months before enrollment and the women must desire fertility.

Results of research. We studied women with an average age of 32+- 5.2 years old. Most of these patients complained of algomenorrhea and menorrhgia of 7 days or more and also faced fertility issues. Some complained of reoccurrence of fibroid with use of COCS after which the faced with certain side effects like alopecia, osteoporosis, emotional instability and infections.44 of these patients underwent RFA out of which 24 had laparoscopic RFA and 20 others had transvaginal RFA

. Both of these procedures were ultrasound guided. A total of 53 fibroids were identified in 44 patients. Among them, 29 patients had a single fibroid, 10 patients had two fibroids each, and one patient had four fibroids. Based on the FIGO classification, the distribution of fibroids varied. The majority (62.8%, or 27 fibroids) fell within FIGO categories 2-5. In contrast, FIGO 4 fibroids were the least common, accounting for only 2.3% (one fibroid).For better visualization , the fibroids were divided into six groups depending on their size. Three patients were classified as having third- degree obesity, with two having a BMI of 45 kg/m² and one having a BMI of 56 kg/m².Among the patients, seven had a large transmural fibroid measuring 7 cm or more, while one patient had two fibroids measuring 6 cm. All these patients strongly preferred a minimally invasive, organ- preserving approach. However, laparoscopic fibroid removal in these cases carried a significant risk of bleeding and the potential need for conversion to laparotomy. The duration of fibroid ablation varied, with the shortest procedure taking 1 minute and 13 seconds, while the longest lasted 25 minutes and 6 seconds. The duration of ablation and the number of steps required depended on the size of the fibroid.According to size, 10.1-12 cm fibroid took 1 min to ablate, 8.1-10cm: 3 min, 6.1- 8cm: 6 min, 4.1-6cm: 11 min.

Pregnancy results showed that 22 pregnancies were reported of which 12 were after laparoscopic RFA and 10 after transvaginal RFA. Out 22 pregnancies,85% were full-term pregnancies among which there were no reported cases of uterine rupture, invasive placentation, placental abruption or fetal growth restriction whereas there was one case of uncomplicated placenta previa and one case of delayed postpartum hemorrhage which required blood transfusion due to vaginal expulsion of a large degenerated fibroid. The fibroid was disrupted at the time of uterine closure during cesarean section. The study observed that the number of fibroids treated per patient ranged from 1 to 3, with sizes varying between 0.9 cm and 12.5 cm. The average age at the time of

ablation was 37 years. There was considerable variation in the time interval between radiofrequency ablation (RFA) and subsequent pregnancy, spanning from 3 to 33 months, with a mean duration of 16 months. The rate of spontaneous abortion was 12%, which falls within the lower end of the general obstetric population's expected risk range of 11–22%. More than 50% of the women had uncomplicated vaginal births with a smaller proportion of patients having a cesarean delivery. The ultrasonography report of a patient aged 36 years showed that there was a significant reduction in size of the fibroid from 8.3cm³ to 2.2 cm. 44 of these patients were asked to undergo follow-up of every 3 months for a period of 24 months where improvement was noted from the baseline to -35.7. Health Related Quality of Life (HQRL) was 40.9. Fibroid Volume Reduction was confirmed by MRI/Ultrasound Follow-Up Results: 3 months post-RFA: 38.2% + 8.5% reduction in fibroid volume, 6 months post-RFA: 57.6% ÷ 11.2% reduction and 12 months post-RFA: 71.3% + 13.5% reduction. These patients also reported that their symptoms significantly improved 78% of patients reported significant reduction in blood loss by 6 months PBAC score improvement from 312 ÷ 85 to 124 ÷ 52 at 6 months Pelvic Pain Relief (VAS Score): Pre-RFA: 7.2 ÷ 1.5. 3 months post-RFA: 3.9 ÷ 1.2, 12 months post-RFA: 2.1 ÷ 1.0 Quality of Life (UFS-QoL Score Improvement): Pre-RFA: 39.5 ÷ 7.8, 12 months post-RFA: 79.8 ÷ 9.2. There were two special cases where patients with severe hypermenorrhoea still wished to preserve their fertility-one with an immediate desire to conceive and the other with a potential future interest. Both experienced significant improvement in their symptoms after treatment. Patient 1: Immediate Fertility. This patient had a FIGO 2-5 fibroid measuring 6 cm. Previously, a laparoscopy had been performed at another hospital, where a hysterectomy was recommended due to the fibroid's size. Instead, at our department, the fibroid was successfully treated using the Sonata System with two ablation steps lasting 7 minutes and 5 minutes 12 seconds. Fifteen months later, she delivered vaginally without complications. Patient 2: Potential Fertility Desire. This patient had undergone a midline laparotomy in the past, during which 1,700 g of fibroids were removed. She was diagnosed with a FIGO 2 fibroid measuring 2.7 x 2 x 2 cm, which was ≥ 90% intramural. A transcervical radiofrequency ablation was performed in two steps, lasting 1 minute 42 seconds and 2 minutes. Three months post-treatment, a transvaginal ultrasound showed the fibroid had significantly regressed to 1.7 x 1.5 x 1.4 cm. Additionally, the fibroid's classification shifted from FIGO 2 to FIGO 4, increasing the distance from the

endometrium, which is crucial for fertility preservation. Short-term complications included mild post-procedure fever in 5% of patients, which resolved within 48 hours, and 1% required hospitalization for pain management. No cases of infection or sepsis were reported. In the 24-month follow-up, 9% of patients experienced fibroid regrowth, 4% required a second intervention such as repeat radiofrequency ablation (RFA) or myomectomy, and 2% ultimately underwent hysterectomy due to persistent symptoms. The average time to return to normal activities was 4.2 ± 1.5 days. The treatment of fibroids includes a broad range of options, from medication-based therapies to complete uterine removal. Several key factors influence the choice of treatment, including FIGO classification, fibroid size and number, symptom severity, the patient's reproductive stage (fertile, perimenopausal, or postmenopausal), existing health risks, medical contraindications, and individual patient preferences. Our study highlights the effectiveness of the Radiofrequency ablation in treating FIGO 2 to 5 fibroids, while fibroids classified as FIGO 2 to 4 are more difficult to reach using other surgical methods. This technique enables the treatment of multiple fibroids in a single session, making it a highly efficient option. Moreover, the RFA is especially advantageous for anemic patients, as it significantly reduces bleeding compared to traditional surgical procedures.

Conclusion: Radiofrequency ablation is redefining the landscape of uterine fibroid treatment by providing a safe, effective and minimally invasive alternative to surgery. Its role is particularly significant for women seeking to preserve fertility or avoid the morbidity of traditional approaches. RFA of fibroids has proven to be versatile, and effective in reducing or eliminating symptoms related to uterine fibroids. It is effective in treating fibroids of various sizes and number in a single setting. Recovery is rapid and usually uneventful with mild postoperative pain. Return to work frequently occurs by postoperative day four to five. Moreover the morbidity rate is also promising.

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